

HYBRID INORGANIC/ORGANIC NANOCOMPOSITES CONSISTING OF CUINS₂-ZNS CORE-SHELL QUANTUM DOTS EMBEDDED IN A POLY(METHYLMETHACRYLATE) MATRIX

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Abstract

CuInS₂ (CIS) - ZnS core-shell quantum dots (QDs) were formed by a using sol-gel method, and nanocomposites consisting of CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs embedded in the poly(methymethacrylate) (PMMA) matrix were formed by a using spin-coating method. A absorption peak at 550 nm for the absorbance spectra corresponded to the optical excitation edge of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs. A peak at 700 nm for the PL spectrum was related to the recombination luminescence of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs. Capacitance-voltage curves for Al/CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in PMMA/p-Si device showed a hysteresis behavior with a flat band voltage shift.

1. Introduction

Hybrid inorganic/organic nanocomposites have been currently receiving considerable attention because of their promising applications in flexible electronic devices operating at lower powers [1-7]. The prospect of potential applications in electronic devices has led to substantial research and development efforts to form various nanocomposites containing inorganic nanocomposites, acting as charge storage regions [8-12]. Nanocomposites containing core-shell quantum dots (QDs) have emerged as excellent candidates for promising applications in electronic devices. Among the several types of QDs, CuInS₂(CIS)-ZnS ternary core-shell QDs have been particularly interesting

due to their being environment-friendly materials in comparison with core-shell QDs containing Cd and Pb atoms and to their promising applications in next-generation electronic devices. Even though some studies concerning the formation and the materials characteristics of binary core-binary shell QDs/polymer nanocomposites have been conducted [13-16], very few works on the formation and the applications of the ternary core-binary shell QDs/polymer nanocomposites have been performed. This paper reports data for formation processes and feasibility results of the hybrid nanocomposites consisting of CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs embedded in the poly(methymethacrylate) (PMMA) matrix for possible applications in nonvolatile memory devices. Absorbance and photoluminescence (PL) measurements were carried out to investigate the optical properties of CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs. Capacitance-voltage (C-V) measurements were performed to investigate the possibility for applications of nanocomposites consisting of core-shell CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in a PMMA matrix in nonvolatile memory devices.

2. Experimental Details

Inorganic/organic nanocomposites consisting of the colloidal CIS-ZnS QDs and the PMMA polymer layer used in this study were prepared on p-Si (100) substrates. The formation process of the CIS-ZnS QDs solution was started by using a CIS core solution [17]. The solution consisting of 8 ml of

octadecene (ODE), 0.1 mMol of indium acetate, and 0.3 mMol of miristic acid were mixed in a 25-ml three-neck flask. Then, the mixed solution was degassed at 110°C for 2 h and was injected with a Cu-thiol stock solution at 250°C. The schematic diagrams of the formation processes of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs are shown in Fig. 1. Subsequently, the solution was heated at 200-210°C for 2 h. 0.3 mMol of copper iodide, was mixed with 3 ml of dodecanethiol, for the synthesis of the Cu-thiol stock solution. Then, the mixed solution was slightly heated on a hot-plate while being stirred. After the synthesis of the CIS core solution was finished, the synthesized solution was in-situ cooled to form the ZnS shell at room temperature. Zn acetate, 0.5 mMol, was added to the CIS core solution, and the solution was heated to 230°C. Then, the solution was aged for 1.5 h at 230°C. To fabricate the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs blended with a PMMA layer, The 150 mg PMMA polymer insulator was dissolved in chlorobenzene (4.85 g) solvent for a 3 wt% PMMA solution. Then, CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs (5.5 mg) blended into PMMA solution. Subsequently, ultrasonication was performed for over 1 h to obtain uniform solutions. The blended solutions treated by using ultrasonic were spin-coated on p-Si substrates. The schematic diagrams of the formation processes of the nanocomposites of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs embedded in a PMMA are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. A schematic of the formation processes of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs.

The schematic diagrams of (a) the CIS-ZnS core-cell nanoparticles and (b) nanocomposites of CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs embedded in PMMA matrix and the chemical structure of the PMMA layer are shown in Fig. 3 [18].

Fig. 2. A schematic of the formation processes of nanocomposites consisting of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs.

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic diagrams of the CIS-ZnS QDs and (b) nanocomposites consisting of CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in a PMMA matrix and the chemical structure of PMMA.

The optical absorption measurements were performed by using an ultraviolet-visible spectrometer (Scinco PDA S-3100). The PL measurements were carried out using a 75 cm monochromator equipped with a GaAs photomultiplier tube (Ocean Optics usb-400). The excitation source was the 355 nm line of a CWUV laser. C-V measurements were performed by using an HP 4284 precision LCR meter at room temperature.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 4 shows optical absorbance and PL spectra of CIS-ZnS core-cell QDs. The broad absorption peak

at 550 nm for the absorbance spectrum corresponds to the optical excitation edge of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs [17, 19]. The dominant peak at 700 nm for the PL spectrum is related to the recombination luminescence due to the interband transitions of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs [17, 19]. The Stöck shift corresponding to the difference of the peak position between the absorbance and the PL spectra might be attributed to the quantum confinement effect of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs, but that is not yet clear.

Fig. 4. Optical absorbance and photoluminescence spectra of CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs.

Al top and bottom electrodes with a thickness of 180 nm were thermally deposited in order to investigate the memory effects of the devices through a metal mask at a system pressure of 1×10^{-6} Torr. Figure 5 shows the C-V curves measured at 1-MHz for the Al/core-shell CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in PMMA layer/p-Si device at room temperature. The C-V behavior of the devices based on the CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in a PMMA layer is similar to those of metal-insulator-semiconductor diodes with floating gates containing nanoparticles [20]. The C-V curves for the Al/core-shell CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in PMMA layer/p-Si device, obtained by sweeping the applied voltage between the inversion and the accumulation regions at room temperature, clearly show counterclockwise hysteresis behavior. The appearance of the C-V hysteresis indicates the existence of charge sites occupied by electrons injected from the inversion layer in the p-Si substrate. However, the Al/PMMA/p-Si device without the core-shell CIS-ZnS QDs shows no hysteresis under same measurement conditions, indicative of the charge storage in the core-shell

CIS-ZnS QDs embedded in a PMMA layer. The memory effect of the counterclockwise hysteresis is attributed to electrons tunneled from the p-Si substrate through PMMA matrix layer and trapped in the core-shell CuInS₂-ZnS QDs [21].

Fig. 5. C-V curves at 9 V with 1-MHz for the CIS-ZnS QDs blended in PMMA/p-Si device.

4. Summary and Conclusions

CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs were formed by using a sol-gel method, and the hybrid nanocomposites consisting of CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs embedded in the PMMA matrix were formed on p-Si (100) substrates by using a spin-coating method. The broad absorption at 550 nm for the absorbance spectrum corresponded to the optical excitation edge of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs. The dominant peak at 700 nm for the PL spectrum was related to the recombination luminescence due to the interband transitions of the CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs. C-V characteristics of the devices fabricated utilizing CIS-ZnS core-shell QDs embedded in a PMMA matrix showed that the hysteresis behavior of the C-V curves was attributed to the carriers captured in the CIS-ZnS QDs. The nanocomposites based on the CIS-ZnS QDs in the PMMA matrix offer possible applications in nonvolatile memory devices.

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References

- [1] H. Y. Jeong, J. Y. Kim, J. W. Kim, J. O. Hwang, J. E. Kim, J. Y. Lee, T. H. Yoon, B. J. Cho, S. O. Kim, R. S. Ruoff and S. Y. Choi "Graphene oxide thin films for flexible nonvolatile memory applications". *Nano Lett.*, Vol. 10, No. 11, pp 4381-4386, 2010.
- [2] K. Asadi, M. Li, N. Lin, P. W. M. Blom and D. M. de Leeuw "Crossbar memory array of organic bistable rectifying diodes for nonvolatile data storage". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 97, No. 19, pp 193308-1 - 193308-3, 2010.
- [3] T. Kimura and M. Hara "Nonvolatile multiple-valued memory device using lateral spin valve". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 97, No. 18, pp 182501-1 - 182501-3, 2010.
- [4] S. William, M. F. Mabrook and D. M. Taylor "Floating-gate memory based on an organic metal-insulator-semiconductor capacitor". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 95, No. 09, pp 093309-1 - 093309-3, 2009.
- [5] F. Lindner, K. Walzer and K. Leo "Organic heterostructure device with nonvolatile memory behavior using electrically doped layers". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 93, No. 23, pp 233305-1 - 233305-3, 2008.
- [6] W. L. Leong, P. S. Lee, S. G. Mhaisalkar, T. P. Chen and A. Dodabalapur "Charging phenomena in pentacene-gold nanoparticle memory device". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 90, No. 4, pp 042906-1 - 042906-3, 2007.
- [7] A. Kanwal and M. Chhowalla "Stable, three layered organic memory devices from C₆₀ molecules and insulating polymers". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 89, No. 20, pp 203103-1 - 203103-3, 2006.
- [8] A. Tang, F. Teng, Y. Hou, Y. Yang, F. Tan, S. Qu and Z. Wang "Optical properties and electrical bistability of CdS nanoparticles synthesized in dodecanethiol". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 96, No. 16, pp 163112-1 - 163112-3, 2010.
- [9] F. Li, D. I. Son, J. H. Ham, G. J. Kim, J. H. Jung and T. W. Kim "Memory effect of nonvolatile bistable devices based on CdSe/ZnS nanoparticles sandwiched between C₆₀ layers". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 91, No. 16, pp 162109-1 - 162109-3, 2007.
- [10] K. Mohanta, S. Majee, S. Batabyal and A. Pal "Electrical bistability in electrostatic assemblies of CdSe nanoparticles". *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, Vol. 110, No. 37, pp 18231-18235, 2006.
- [11] J. H. Kim, J. Y. Jin, J. H. Jung, I. Lee, T. W. Kim, S. K. Lim, C. S. Yoon and Y. H. Kim "Formation and electrical properties of Ni_{1-x}Fe_x nanocrystals embedded in a polyimide layers for applications as nonvolatile flash memories". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 86, No. 3, pp 032904-1 - 032904-3, 2005.
- [12] N. J. Craig, J. M. Taylor, E. A. Lester, C. M. Marcus, M. P. Hanson and A. C. Gossard "Tunable nonlocal spin control in a coupled-quantum dot system". *Science*, Vol. 304, No. 23, pp 565-567, 2004.
- [13] F. Li, D. I. Son, T. W. Kim, E. Ryu and S. W. Kim "Carrier transport mechanisms of bistable memory devices fabricated utilizing core-shell CdSe/ZnSe quantum-dot/multi-walled carbon nanotube hybrid nanocomposites". *Nanotechnology*, Vol. 20, No. 8, pp 085202-1 - 085202-5, 2009.
- [14] V. S. Reddy, S. Karak and A. Dhara "Multilevel conductance switching in organic memory devices based on Alq₃ and Al/Al₂O₃ core-shell nanoparticles". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 94, No. 17, pp 173304-1 - 173304-3, 2009.
- [15] H. Liu, W. Winkenwerder, Y. Liu, D. Ferrer, D. Shahrjerdi, S. K. Stanley, J. G. Ekerdt and S. K. Banerjee "Core-shell germanium-silicon nanocrystal floating gate for nonvolatile memory application". *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices*, Vol. 55, No. 12, pp 3610-3614, 2008.
- [16] F. Li, D. I. Son, S. M. Seo, H. M. Cha, H. J. Kim, B. J. Kim, J. H. Jung and T. W. Kim "Organic bistable devices based on core/shell CdSe/ZnS nanoparticles embedded in a conducting poly(N-vinylcarbazole) polymer layer". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 91, No. 12, pp 122111-1 - 122111-3, 2007.
- [17] J. H. Park and S. W. Kim "CuInS₂/ZnS core/shell quantum dots by cation exchange and their blue-shifted photoluminescence" *J. Mater. Chem.*, Vol. 21, pp 3745-3750, 2011.
- [18] D. I. Son, D. H. Park, S. Y. Ie, W. K. Choi, J. W. Choi, F. Li and T. W. Kim "Single active-layer structured dual-function devices using hybrid polymer-quantum dots" *Nanotechnology*, Vol. 19, No. 39, pp 395201-1 - 395201-7, 2008.
- [19] R. Xie, M. Rutherford, and X. Peng "Formation of high-quality I-III-VI semiconductor nanocrystals by tuning relative reactivity of cationic precursors", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, Vol. 131, No. 16, pp. 5691-5697, 2009.
- [20] M. Kanoun, A. Souifi, T. Baron and F. Mazen "Electrical study of Ge-nanocrystal-based metal-oxide-semiconductor structures for p-type nonvolatile memory applications". *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 84, No. 25, pp 5079-5081, 2004.
- [21] S. Nakata, K. Saito and M. Shimada "Non-volatile Al₂O₃ memory using nanoscale Al-rich Al₂O₃ thin film as a charge storage layer". *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 45, No. 4B, pp 3176-3178, 2006.